

**MAGNIT MAYDONIDA PLASTINKANING MAGNETOELASTIK
DEFORMATSIYA JARAYONINI MATEMATIK MADELLASHTIRISH****Abdullaev Abdubakir Xikmatillayevich**

Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari
universiteti, Elektronika va radiotexnika kafedrasida assistenti

abdullayev@tuit.uz

ANNOTATSIYA. Mazkur maqolada tok o'tkazuvchan halqali egiluvchan plastinkaga turli ta'sir etuvchi kuchlar hamda magnit maydonning plastinkaga ta'siri masalalariga bag'ishlangan. Anizotrop elektr o'tkazuvchanligini hisobga olgan holda vaqtda o'zgaruvchan mexanik kuch va tashqi elektr toki ta'sirida, tok o'tkazuvchi egiluvchan halqali plastinka matematik tarzda tadqiq qilingan. Tashqi magnit maydonning halqasimon plastinkaning kuchlanganlik holatiga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Masalani hal qilishda sonli qiymatlar orqali hisoblash amalga oshirilgan.

KALIT SO'ZLAR. Plastinka, magnit maydon, magnitoelastiklik, halqasimon plastinka

АННОТАЦИЯ. В данной статье рассматриваются различные силы, действующие на гибкую пластину с токоведущим кольцом, и воздействие магнитного поля на пластину. В статье с учетом анизотропной электропроводности под действием переменной во времени механической силы и внешнего электрического тока математически моделируется токонесящая гибкая кольцевая пластина. Исследовано влияние внешнего магнитного поля на напряженное состояние кольцевой пластины. При решении задачи расчет проводился с использованием численных значений.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА. пластина, магнитное поле, магнитоупругость, кольцевая пластина

ABSTRACT. This article deals with various forces acting on a flexible plate with a current-carrying ring and the effects of a magnetic field on the plate. Taking into account the anisotropic electrical conductivity, under the influence of time-varying mechanical force and external electric current, the current-carrying flexible ring plate is mathematically simulated in the article. The influence of an external magnetic field on the stress state of the annular plate is studied. In solving the problem, the calculation was carried out using numerical values.

KEY WORDS. plate, magnetic field, magneto elasticity, annular plate

KIRISH

Bugungi kunda jahon miqyosida zamonaviy texnikada optimal konstruksiyalarni yaratish chiziqli bo‘lmagan qonuniyat bilan o‘zgarayotgan ta’sirni hisobga olgan holda yupqa plastinka shaklidagi konstruktiv elementlarning keng ravishda ishlab chiqarishda qo‘llanilishi dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Horijiy yetakchi ilmiy markazlarda magnit maydoni bilan elastik muhitning o‘zaro ta’sir mexanizmlari, qaralayotgan jismning geometrik xususiyatlari hamda fizikaviy xossalari bog‘liq holdagi masalalar yuzasidan bir qancha nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. Xususan, bu ta’sir mexanizmini tadqiq etish muammoli masalalardan biri sifatida anizotrop elektr o‘tkazuvchanlik yupqa plastinkalarga nisbatan qaralganda bir qancha maxsus xususiyatlarga ega bo‘ladi.

Qattiq elektr materiallari turli tuzilishga ega bo‘lishi mumkin - kristall, amorf va kompozit. Kristallar bir xil fazoviy hujayralarning qat’iy takrorlanishi va elektrostatik maydonning davriyligi bilan tavsiflanadi. Kristallar atomlar olamidagi poklik va tartib namunasidir; ular fazoviy panjaralar shaklida farqlanadi va har xil turdagi simmetriyaga ega.

Yagona kristallar anizotropiyaga ega; ularning elektr, magnit, yorug‘lik, mexanik va boshqa ta’sirlarga bo‘lgan reaksiyalari bu ta’sirlarning kristallning kristallografik tekisliklari va o‘qlariga nisbatan yo‘nalishiga bog‘liq.

Yagona kristallar yanada mukammal tuzilish bilan ajralib turadi, ular eng ko'p o'rganilganlardir, ularda sodir bo'ladigan fizik hodisalar osongina hisoblab chiqiladi; ular yarimo'tkazgichli qurilmalarning ko'proq ishonchliligi va parametrlarining identifikatsiyasini ta'minlaydi.

Magnit yarim o'tkazgichlarda zaryad tashuvchilarning hosil bo'lish jarayonlari va elektr tokining o'tishi magnit maydon induksiyasining yo'nalishi va qiymatiga bog'liq.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Metall magnit materiallar elektr tokini o'tkazadi. O'zgaruvchan maydonlarda ularda chastotali ortib borayotgan oqimlar paydo bo'ladi, shuning uchun ulardan foydalanish chastota diapazoni to'g'ridan-to'g'ri oqim qurilmalari, shuningdek sanoat va audio chastotali oqimlari bilan cheklangan. Elektron qurilmalarning mikrominiatizatsiyasi nanotexnologiyalar rivojlanishi uchun kuchli rag'batdir va mikroelektronika bizning ko'z o'ngimizda nanoelektronikaga aylanmoqda. So'nggi o'n yilliklarda adabiyotda statsionar bo'lmagan kuch, issiqlik va elektromagnit yuklar ta'sirida tashqi o'zgaruvchan magnit maydonga joylashtirilgan elektr o'tkazuvchan jismlarning deformatsiyalanish jarayonini o'rganishga katta e'tibor berildi. [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22]. Ushbu sohadagi tadqiqotlarga qiziqish statsionar bo'lmagan mexanik, issiqlik va elektromagnit jarayonlarning kuzatilgan ta'sirini miqdoriy jihatdan o'rganish va baholash hamda ularni yangi texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqishda, nanotexnologiya va mikroelektronika sohasida, zamonaviy o'lchash tizimlarida va boshqa sohalarida amaliy qo'llash muhimligi bilan bog'liq.

Ortotropik elektr o'tkazuvchanlikka ega bo'lgan ortotropik plastinkalarning magnit elastikligining bog'langan muammolarini sonli hal qilishning ishlab chiqilgan usullari, Nyumark, chiziq lashtirish usuli va turg'un bo'lgan diskret ortogonallashtirish usullari qo'llaniladi[2-6,9].

O'zgaruvchilarni vaqt koordinatasidan ajratish uchun biz nochiziqli chegaraviy masala har bir vaqt bosqichida chiziqli bo'lmagan bir o'lchovli chegara masalalari

ketma-ketligiga qisqaradigan noaniq Nyumark sxemasini qo'llaymiz. Magnit elastiklikning chiziqli bo'lmagan chegaraviy masalalari ketma-ketligini yechishning navbatdagi bosqichi chiziqashtirish usulini qo'llashga asoslangan bo'lib, uning yordamida chiziqli bo'lmagan chegaraviy masala chiziqli chegaraviy masalalar ketma-ketligiga kamayadi. Keyin tegishli vaqt oralig'idagi ketma-ketlikning chiziqli chegaraviy masalalarining har biri diskret ortogonallashtirish usuli yordamida sonli hal qilinadi.

NATIJALAR (Moslashuvchan o'tkazgichli halqasimon plastinkaning asosiy magnetoelastik tenglamalari)

Yupqa qobiqning magnit elastiklik munosabatlari [3] asosida va chiziqli bo'lmagan elastiklik munosabatlari, shuningdek, Om qonuni va Maksvell tenglamalaridan foydalangan holda, o'tkazuvchi halqali plastinkaning asosiy tenglamalarini quyidagicha olish mumkin: Magnit elastik kinetik tenglamalar quyidagi ko'rinishga ega:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(rN_r)}{\partial r} - N_0 + r(F_r + \rho F_r^{\wedge}) &= r\rho h \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2}; \quad \frac{\partial(rQ_r)}{\partial r} + r(F_z + \rho F_z^{\wedge}) = r\rho h \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2}; \\ \frac{\partial(rM_r)}{\partial r} - M_0 - rQ_r - rN_r \vartheta_r &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Elektrodinamika tenglamalari:

$$-\frac{\partial B_z}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(rE_r)}{\partial r}; \quad \sigma_2 \left[E_0 + 0,5 \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} (B_r^+ + B_r^-) - \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} B_z \right] = -\frac{\partial H_z}{\partial t} + \frac{H_r^+ - H_r^-}{h}. \quad (2)$$

Deformatsiyalar uchun ifodalar:

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \vartheta_r^2; \quad \varepsilon_\theta = \frac{u}{r}; \quad \chi_r = \frac{\partial \vartheta_r}{\partial r}; \quad \chi_\theta = \frac{1}{r} \vartheta_\theta; \quad (3)$$

bu yerda, $\vartheta_\theta = \partial w / \partial r$ normal burilish burchagi;

Elastiklik nisbati:

$$N_r = \frac{e_r h}{1 - \nu_r \nu_\theta} (\varepsilon_r + \nu_\theta \varepsilon_\theta); \quad N_\theta = \frac{e_\theta h}{1 - \nu_r \nu_\theta} (\varepsilon_\theta + \nu_r \varepsilon_r);$$

$$M_r = \frac{e_r h^3}{12(1-\nu_r \nu_\theta)} (\chi_r + \nu_\theta \chi_\theta); \quad M_\theta = \frac{e_\theta h^3}{12(1-\nu_r \nu_\theta)} (\chi_\theta + \nu_r \chi_r). \quad (4)$$

(1)–(4) tenglamalarda quyidagi parametrlar qabul qilinadi: $\nu_r = \nu_{\theta r}$, $\nu_\theta = \nu_{r\theta}$, $\varepsilon_r \nu_\theta = \varepsilon_\theta \nu_r$; ν_r , ν_θ – Poisson nisbatlari; ε_r , ε_θ – Young moduli; u , w – siljishlar; N_r , N_θ – tangensial kuchlar; M_r , M_θ – egilish momentlari; Q_r – umumlashtirilgan kesish kuchi; χ_r , χ_θ – plastinkaning o'rta yuzasining asosiy egriliklari; B_r^\pm – plastinkaning sirtlarida magnit induksiyaning tangensial komponentlarining ma'lum qiymatlari.

Lorents kuchining ifodalari quyidagi shaklga ega:

$$\rho F_r^\wedge = \sigma_1 h \left[E_\theta B_z - \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} B_z^2 + 0,5 \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} (B_r^+ + B_r^-) B_z \right];$$

$$\rho F_z^\wedge = -\sigma_2 h \left[0,5 E_\theta (B_r^+ + B_r^-) - 0,25 \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} (B_r^+ + B_r^-)^2 - \frac{1}{12} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} (B_r^+ + B_r^-)^2 + 0,5 \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} (B_r^+ + B_r^-) B_z \right]; \quad (5)$$

MUHOKAMA (Elektromagnit elastiklik ta'sirlarning tahlili)

Quyidagi $h = 5 \cdot 10^{-4} (1 - \gamma r^2 / r_0) m$ qonuniga ko'ra meridional yo'nalishda o'zgaruvchan qalinlikdagi halqasimon shaklidagi bor alyuminiy plastinkasining chiziqli bo'lmagan harakatini ko'rib chiqamiz. Plastinkani $P_\xi = 5 \cdot 10^3 \sin \omega t N/m^2$ mexanik kuch ta'sirida deb hisoblaymiz, uning tashqi elektr toki $J_{\theta CT} = 3 \cdot 10^7 \sin \omega t A/m^2$, tashqi magnit maydoni $B_{s0} = 0,1 T$, va plastinka elastik ortotropik va cheklangan ortotropik elektr o'tkazuvchanligi $\sigma(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3)$ ga ega. Buzilmagan holat uchun tashqi va ichki boshlang'ich holatning magnit induksiya vektorlarining ma'lum qiymatlari uchun magnitostatika masalasi hal qilinsin.

Biz buzilmagan holatda tashqi elektr tokini plastinka ustida bir tekis taqsimlangan deb hisoblaymiz, ya'ni tashqi oqim zichligi koordinatalarga bog'liq emas. Bunday holda, plastinka Lorentz ponderomotor kuchi va mexanik kuchdan tashkil topgan qo'shma yukga duchor bo'ladi.

Keling, tashqi magnit maydonning halqali plastinkaning kuchlanish holatiga ta'sirini o'rganamiz.

Chegara shartlari:

$$s = r_0 = 0, \quad u = 0, \quad w = 0, \quad \mathcal{G}_r = 0, \quad B_z = 0.5 \sin \omega t;$$

$$s = r_N = 0.0009 m: \quad N_r = 0; \quad Q_r = -100, \quad M_r = 0, \quad E_\theta = 0.$$

Dastlabki shartlar:

$$\vec{N}(s, t)|_{t=0} = 0, \quad \dot{u}(s, t)|_{t=0} = 0, \quad \dot{w}(s, t)|_{t=0} = 0.$$

Plastinka va materialning parametrlari:

$$r_0 = 0.005 m, \quad r_1 = 0.009 m, \quad h = 5 \cdot 10^{-4} (1 - \gamma r^2 / r_0) m; \quad \gamma = 0.7,$$

$$\sigma_1 = 0.454 \cdot 10^8 (\Omega \times m)^{-1}, \quad \sigma_2 = 0.200 \cdot 10^8 (\Omega \times m)^{-1}, \quad \nu_r = 0.262, \quad \nu_\theta = 0.320;$$

$$e_r = 22.9 \cdot 10^{10} N/m^2; \quad e_\theta = 10.7 \cdot 10^{10} N/m^2; \quad \omega = 314.16 \text{sek}^{-1}; \quad P_z = 5 \cdot 10^3 \sin \omega t \text{ H/M}^2;$$

$$P_r = 0; \quad \tau = 1 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{sek}; \quad \mu = 1.256 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ H/M};$$

$$\rho = 2600 \text{ kg/m}^3; \quad J_{\text{OCT}} = 3 \cdot 10^7 \sin \omega t \text{ A/m}^2; \quad B_r^\pm = 0.5 T/\pi; \quad B_{r0} = 0.5 \sin \omega t;$$

$$\Delta t = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{sek}; \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{sek}.$$

Muammoni hal qilish $\tau = 10^{-2}$ sek vaqt oralig'ida aniqlanadi, vaqt bo'yicha integratsiya qadami qobiq uzunligi bo'ylab yuzta integratsiya nuqtasida $\Delta t = 1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ sek sifatida qabul qilinadi. 1-rasmda magnit induksiyasining uchta qiymati uchun Lorents kuchi $F_r^\wedge(t)$ normal komponentining vaqt o'zgarishi grafiklari keltirilgan. 1 ÷ 3 grafiklar magnit induksiyasiga mos ravishda 1. $B_{z0} = 0.1$; 2. $B_{z0} = 0.2$; 3. $B_{z0} = 0.5$ ga mos keladi.

1- rasm. Tashqi magnit induksiyasining normal komponenti qiymatlari uchun Lorents kuchining normal komponenti $F_r^{\wedge}(t)$ vaqt o'zgarishi grafiklari

Olingan sonli natijalarni tahlil qilib, tashqi magnit induksiyaning normal komponenti qiymatlari ortishi bilan Lorentz kuchi ortib borishini ko'rish mumkin.

Aniqlanishicha, tashqi magnit induksiya qiymatining oshishi bilan plastinkaning tashqi yuzasidagi kuchlanishlar Lorentz kuchining yo'nalishi o'zgarishiga va mexanik yuk bilan o'zaro ta'sirga qarab o'zgaradi.

XULOSA

Maqolada o'tkazuvchanlik xususiyatlarining anizotropiyasini hisobga olgan holda egiluvchan ortotropik o'tkazuvchan halqali plastinka uchun magnit elastiklikning birlashtirilgan muammosi ko'rib chiqildi. Anizotrop elektr o'tkazuvchanligini hisobga olgan holda halqasimon plastinkaning magnit elastikligining chiziqli bo'lmagan muammosi uchun yechim olindi.

Olingan natijalarni tahlil qilish bizga magnit induksiyaning oddiy komponentlarining moslashuvchan ortotropik halqali plastinkaning kuchlanish

holatiga ta'sirini baholash imkonini beradi. Taqdim etilgan natijalarga asoslanib, o'tkazgichli halqali plastinka uchun magnit elastik chiziqli bo'lmagan muammoni birlashtirilgan shaklda ko'rib chiqish kerak.

Adabiyotlar

1. Ambartsumyan, G.E. Bagdasaryan, & Belubekyan, M.V. (1977). *Magnetoelasticity of Thin Shells and Plates* [in Russian]. Moscow: Nauka.
2. Grigorenko, Y. M., & Mol'chenko, L. V. (2010). *Fundamentals of the Theory of Plates and Shells with Elements of Magnetoelasticity (Textbook) (IPTs)*.
3. Mol'chenko, L. V., Loos, I. I., & Indiaminov, R. S. (2008). "Determining the stress state of flexible orthotropic shells of revolution in magnetic field," *Int. Appl. Mech* 44, 882–891. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10778-008-0102-6>
4. Indiaminov, R. (2008). "On the absence of the tangential projection of the lorenz force on the axsymmetrical stressed state of current-carrying conic shells," *Int. Jour. Comp. Techn.* 13, 65–77.
5. Mol'chenko, L. V., Loos, I. I., & Indiaminov, R.S. (2009). "Stress–strain state of flexible ring plates of variable stiffness in a magnetic field," *Int. Appl. Mech.* 45, 1236–1242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10778-010-0264-x>
6. Mol'chenko, L. V., & Loos, I. I. (2013). "The stress state of a flexible orthotropic spherical shell subject to external current and mechanical force in a magnetic field," *Int. Appl. Mech.* 49, 528–533.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10778-013-0587-5>
7. Mol'chenko, L. V., Loos, I. I., & Fedorchenko, L. M. (2016). "Deformation of a flexible orthotropic spherical shell of variable stiffness in a magnetic field," *Int. Appl. Mech* 52, 56–61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10778-016-0732-z>
8. Bian, Y. H., & Zhao, H. T. (2016). "Analysis of thermal-magnetic-elastic stresses and strains in a thin current-carrying cylindrical shell," *Int. Appl. Mech.*, 52, No. 4, –P 437-448.

9. Indiaminov, R. S. (2015). “Magnetoelastic deformation of a current-carrying orthotropic conical shell with an orthotropy of conductive properties,” *Bulletin of the University of Kiev* 5, –P.81–86.

10. Indiaminov, R., Butaev, R., & Mavlanov, S. (2018). “Research of deformation of the current carrying orthotropic shells in nonlinear statement,” *ISJ Theoretical, Applied Science* 09(65), –P.25–30. doi.org/10.15863/TAS. <https://doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2018.09.65.5>

11. Indiaminov, R. S., & Butaev, R. (2020). “Stressstrain state of current-carrying shells in a magnetic field,” *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 05(85), –P.489–492, dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS <https://doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2020.05.85.90>

12. Indiaminov, R., & Rustamov, S. (2019). “Axisymmetric magnetoelastic shellsdeformation with account for anisotropy of conductive properties,” *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 11(79), –P.554–559, doi.org/10.15863/TAS.

<https://doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2019.11.79.115> Google ScholarCrossref

13. Indiaminov, R. S., Narkulov, A. S., & Zarpullaev, U. K. (2020). “Mathematical modeling of magnetoelastic vibrations of a rod in a magnetic field,” *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 03(83), –P.327–332, 10.15863/TAS. <https://doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2020.03.83.60>

14. Indiaminov, R., Kholjigitov, S., & Narkulov, A.S. (2020). “Nonlinear vibrations of a currentcarrying anisotropic cylindrical shell in a magnetic field,” *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science* 01(81), 205–211, 10.15863/TAS. <https://doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2020.01.81.38>

15. Indiaminov, R. S., & Butaev, R. (2020). “Nonlinear integro-differential equations of bending of physically nonlinear viscoelastic plates,” *IOP Publishing. Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, –P.7.

<https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/869/5/052048>

16. Indiaminov, R., Narkulov, A., & Butaev, R. (2021). “Magnetoelastic strain of flexible shells in nonlinear statement”, AIP Conference Proceedings, 2365, 02 0002.

<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0056840>

17. Indiaminov, R., Butaev, R., Narkulov, A., & Abdullaev, A. (2021). “Nonlinear deformation of a current shell in a magnetic field”, AIP Conference Proceedings, 2021, 2365, 02 0001. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0056840>

18. Indiaminov, R., Butaev, R., Narkulov, A., & Abdullaev, A. (2021). “Nonlinear Strain of a Current-Conducting Annular Plate in a Magnetic Field”, AIP Conference Proceedings 2467, 060026 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0092485>

19. [Shodmonov J., Abdullaev A. “Tok o‘tkazuvchi mikroelementning magnitoelastik tebranishi”, International Scientific Journal of “Science and Innovation”. UIF-2022: 8.2. ISSN: 2181-3337. Volume 1, Issue 4. –P.52-55. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6873133>](#)

20. Indiaminov R., Abdullaev A., & [Shodmonov J.](#) “Mathematical Modeling of Magnetoelastic Oscillations of a Current-Carrying Microelement Magnetic Field”, International Journal of Theoretical and Applied Issues of Digital Technologies ISSN 2181-3086, eISSN 2181-3094 № 1(1) 2022. –P.71-79.

https://doi.org/10.34920/IJTAIDT/vol_2022_issue_1_11

21. Indiaminov R., Abdullaev A., & [Shodmonov J.](#) [Mathematical simulation of magnetoelastic deformation of electrically conductive plate in a magnetic field, “Современное состояние и перспективы применения цифровых технологий и искусственного интеллекта в управлении” сборник докладов республиканской научно-технической конференции. Ч.2. Самарканд-2022.–С. 22-28](#)

22. Indiaminov R., Abdullaev A., Ismailova N. “Magnit maydonida tok o‘tkazuvchi jismning magnitoelastik deformatsiyalanishi modeli”, “Zamonaviy matematikaning nazariy asoslari va amaliy masalalari” respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallar to‘plami. Andijon-2022. –B.184-186.

https://file.adu.uz/s/2022/03/conference_math_02.pdf